

LEVELS OF EXPRESSION OF CD31+, CD3+, CD20+ IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL MARKERS IN ADRENAL GLAND TISSUE IN COVID-19

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Abstract. CD31+, CD3+, CD20+ immunohistochemical markers were studied in the adrenal gland tissue in order to study the degree of damage to the adrenal gland caused by COVID-19 infection and the immunological response of the organ against the virus.

Keywords: Adrenal glands, immunohistochemistry, antibody, cortex, expression.

The purpose of the study: To study immunohistochemical changes in cortex of adrenal glands of patients who died of COVID-19 infection.

Materials and methods: The object of the study was the examination and performance of immunohistochemical procedures of isolated adrenal glands during autopsy from 50 patients who died from COVID-19 infection at the Republican Pathological Anatomy Center.

Research results: CD31+ protein is a molecule that adheres to endothelium and platelets. To study the expression of CD31+ protein under the influence of monoclonal antibody, 3 morphofunctional areas of the adrenal cortex were studied separately. In our study, it was observed that all morphofunctional areas of the adrenal cortex were expressed in more than 50% of endothelial cells in the vascular wall. In this case, it was found that it was expressed at the level of 86.5% in glomerulosa zona, 81.4% in fascicular zona, and 79.2% in the reticular zona, and the vessel wall was completely painted in dark brown color. The medium expression level was found to be 11.5% in glomerulosa zona, 14.8% in fascicular zona, and 15.7% in reticular zona. Low-level expression was found to be 2.0% in glomerulosa zona, 3.8% in fascicular zona, and 5.1% in the reticular zona.

In almost all the morphofunctional areas of the adrenal gland cortex that we studied, it was found that the high level of expression of the CD3+ marker was very low in 50% of the cells, it was observed that it was expressed at the level of 1.5% in glomerulosa zona, 2.7% in fascicular zona, and 4.5% in the reticular zona. Medium expression of the CD3+ marker was 8.6% in the glomerulosa zona, 9.5% in fascicular zona, and 7.5% in the reticular zona.

It was found that the CD20+ marker was expressed at the level of 1.2%, 3.7%, and 6.5% accordingly in adrenal cortex. Moderate expression of this marker was observed with 2.6% expression in glomerulosa zona and 8.5% expression in fascicular and reticular areas.

Conclusions. Since the CD31+ marker is present on the endothelial cells of the inner surface of vessels and on almost all white blood cells in the blood, in our study, all morphofunctional areas of the adrenal cortex were expressed at a level higher than 50% of the endothelial cells in the wall of the blood vessels, including 86.5% in glomerulosa zona, 81.4% in fascicular zona and 79.2% in the reticular area were expressed, and it was found that the vessel wall was completely stained dark brown. The percentage of highly expressed cells of the CD3+ marker was expressed at 1.5% in glomerulosa zona, 2.7% in fascicular zona, and 4.5% in the reticular zona. In the case of COVID-19 infection, the immune system decreases, due to the paralysis of B-lymphocytic immunity, it was found that the CD20+

marker was expressed at the level of 1.2%, 3.7% in fascicular zona, and 6.5% in the reticular zona of the adrenal cortex.

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